

A multi-criteria analysis highlights the contrasting effectiveness of conservation and management tools in the small-scale fishery of Peru

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The small-scale fishery in Peru (SSFP) has a huge socio-economic impact on local communities and represents a key source of national employment (Coayla 2020). This activity provides seafood to both local and national markets; however, it has suffered several changes over time due to anthropogenic (overcapacity, unreported and illegal fishery activities) and natural (recurrence of El Niño events) forcing factors (Meyer et al. 2014; Aramayo 2015). In addition, the limited knowledge concerning the effectiveness of certain conservation and management tools (CMTs) hinders our capacity to analyse their role in the sustainability of the sector (Wolff and Mendo 2000; Avadí et al. 2018). We assessed the main CMTs implemented for the SSFP by contrasting their use approach and integrating expert judgement data regarding four thematic axes: the degree of contribution to efficiency, sustainability, conservation, and equity. Major CMTs analyzed were: minimum catch lengths, catch quota, percentage maximum of bycatch, temporary and spatial closures, 5 nm exclusive zone, fishing methods, and natural protected areas (Paracas, San Fernando, Guano Islands, Dorsal de Nazca). In terms of biomass sustainability, the temporary closure was the most effective CMT, followed by the catch quota; while the least effective was the natural protected areas system, together with the 5 nm exclusive zone. Contrastingly, different CMTs were selected when considering their effectiveness in terms of conservation, namely, fishing methods, 5 nm exclusive zone, percentage maximum of bycatch, and the natural protected areas system. Although not conceived so, some CMTs have the potential to improve both the sustainability of the SSFP and the effectiveness in protecting living resources, but there is a critical distinction regarding the dynamic and adaptive strategy involved in each CMT. We also distinguish between static and dynamic CMTs and conclude that static tools and associated strategies should be reanalyzed to ensure their current and future effectiveness concerning poor and limited regulations, rapid distribution changes of exploited species, increasing occurrence of El Niño events, and global environmental uncertainty.

Keywords: conservation and management tools, exploited species, small-scale fishery, marine protected areas, Peru.

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